

Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: Characteristic and clinical perspective

Ichsanto Permadi ^{1,*}, Tri Yudani M.Raras ² and Sumarno Reto Prawiro ³

¹ Department Biomedical Science Post Graduate Programs, Faculty of Medicine Brawijaya University, Malang, East Java, Indonesia.

² Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Faculty of Medicine Brawijaya University, Malang, East Java, Indonesia.

³ Department Clinical Microbiology, Faculty of Medicine Brawijaya University, Malang, East Java, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 19(01), 625–630

Publication history: Received on 31 May 2023; revised on 06 July 2023; accepted on 08 July 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.19.1.1361>

Abstract

Background: *Hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP). A virulent pathogen that has the ability to infect individuals in various age, has multiple ports of entry and cause infectious syndromes. Therefore urges an increase awareness and perspective on the characteristics and clinical feature of hvKP, to better understanding and providing appropriate treatment in cases of infection caused by hvKP.

Main Text: *Hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP) was first reported in Taiwan in 1986. This bacteria was responsible for liver abscess with septic endophthalmitis, of these cases some of patient have extrahepatic complications such as meningitis pneumonia, prostate abscess and pyogenic ophthalmia. There are several virulence factors hvKP such as, capsule as the main defensive factor, aerobactin provide iron supply and Colibactin can suppressing the activity of regulatory T lymphocyte cells, could improve survival hvKP by avoid the process of phagocytosis, complement, antimicrobial peptides and specific antibodies. The pathophysiology and clinical factors of hvKP showed similar symptom to conventional cKP except liver abscess and infectious syndrom.

Conclusion: The threat of *Hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP) increases worldwide due the virulence factors more vary compared to conventional cKP. Consequently, special measures such as vaccine need to be develop in order to eradicate this pathogen particularly among pediatric patient.

Keywords: *Hypervirulent K. pneumoniae*; Liver Abscess; *Hypermucoviscous*; Capsular polysaccharides; hvKP

1. Introduction

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a gram-negative bacterium, family of *Enterobacteriaceae* that causes nosocomial infections, such as pneumonia, meningitis and hospital-acquired urinary tract infections in the United States [1,2]. These bacteria are also responsible in intensive care units in Africa and Singapore [3]. There are some unusual cases such as those that occurred in Taiwan around 1980, where cases liver abscess along with endophthalmitis is a result of hereinafter known as *hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP) [4]. Nowadays hvKP is regarded have high pathogenic and mortality rates [5].

Hypervirulent K. pneumoniae (hvKP) has the ability to resist to neutrophil-mediated phagocytosis when compared with *classic K. pneumoniae* (cKP), it is strongly related to *hypermucoviscous* phenotype [6,7]. *Hypermucoviscous* being one of the main characteristics of hvKP based on string test in agar plates [8]. Related with these characteristics, several studies also found that some hvKP isolates have capsular serotypes K1 and K2, as well several genes that play a role in virulence such as regulators of mucoid phenotype A and A2 (*rmpA*), mucoviscosity-associated gene a (*magA*) and also encoding

* Corresponding author: Ichsanto Permadi

GDP-fucose synthetase (*wcaG*) [9,10]. The phenotypes hvKP are thought to be influenced by virulent plasmids such as pK2044 and pLVPK [11]. Nowadays hvKP is described as a virulent pathogen that has the ability to infect individuals in various age ranges and has multiple ports of entry that can attack multisystem organs and cause infectious syndromes such as non-hepatic abscesses, pneumonia, necrotizing fasciitis, endophthalmitis, and meningitis [12]. Consequently, awareness and perspective on the characteristics and clinical feature of hvKP, are urgently required to get better understanding and providing appropriate treatment in cases of infection caused by hvKP.

2. Overview *Hypervirulent K. pneumoniae*

2.1. History

Based on the genomic analysis 328 isolates *K. pneumoniae* are divided into 3 species, namely *K. pneumoniae*, *K. quasipneumoniae* and *K. variicola*, however only *K. pneumoniae* that are responsible for the majority of human infections, and the hvKP strain is part of the *K. pneumoniae* [13].

Study in Taiwan in 1986 reported as many as 7 clinical cases of liver abscess with septic endophthalmitis caused by *K. pneumoniae*, of these cases some of them have extrahepatic complications such as meningitis pneumonia, prostate abscess and pyogenic ophthalmia [4]. Among 7 individuals 4 of them showed a history of diabetes mellitus, and others were individuals who had no comorbid history. This case became the first reported clinical case that *K. pneumoniae* could to infect multi-system organs with a wide spread of bacteremia.

At the same year, research conducted by Nassif and Sansonetti (1986) found that there are 7 strains of very high virulence *K. pneumoniae* shown by the results of Lethal dose rate of 50% in rats of $<10^3$ CFU [14]. Furthermore, in the study also demonstrated that only *K. pneumoniae* serotypes K1 and K2 demonstrated *hypermucoviscous* phenotypes. This characteristic is proven to be mediated by the capsular polysaccharide regulator *RmpA*, in addition to plasmids containing genes that can produce aerobactin [15].

Fang's found *K. pneumoniae* that cause cases of liver abscess have *hypermucoviscous* phenotype, which is defined through the string test [16]. All the way to *K. pneumoniae* that have a *hypermucoviscous* phenotype, known as *hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP).

2.2. Virulence Factor

There are several factors that affect virulence in hypervirulent *K. pneumoniae*:

2.2.1. Capsules

Based on polysaccharide components hvKP capsules, hvKP are divided into 79 serotypes, of the overall serotype, serotype K1 and K2 are the most commonly encountered in hvKP [17]. Some studies demonstrated serotypes K1 and K2 are highly virulence compared to others because serotypes K1 and K2 do not possess mannose and rhamnose, which are commonly recognized by macrophage leptin receptors in process of phagocytosis [18]. A capsule surrounding the surface of *K. pneumoniae* is a major virulence factor associated with the *hypermucoviscous* phenotype (19). Capsule is the main defensive factor that mediates the occurrence of resistance to bactericidal, thus allowing hvKP to avoid the process of phagocytosis, complement, antimicrobial peptides and specific antibodies [20]. One research showed that hvKP could escape from phagocytosis as well as neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) due to strong *hypermucoviscous* phenotypes mediated by capsular polysaccharide regulators *RmpA* [21]. The fact that size of hvKP capsules is thicker > 2 nm when compared to cKP, in addition to the presence of *hypermucoviscous* allows an increase the viability of hvKP capsules as a physical barrier [22,23]. Truly the components of this capsule hvKP to survive against the immune system and increase its ability to resistance to bactericidal compounds.

2.2.2. Siderophore

Iron is a very essential component for metabolic processes with limited availability in microenvironment. In order to survive and thrive bacteria must make the acquisition of iron from the extracellular host cells [24]. Siderophore is a small molecule synthesized by bacteria that serves as a binder of iron around the bacteria and then transport back into the bacteria [25]. There are four types of siderophore molecules expressed hvKP i.e enterobactin, yerseniabactin, salmochelin, and aerobactin, of these four aerobactin has a dominant proportion (90%) of expression by hvKP [20,26]. Another study also stated that the discovered of *iucABCD* and *iutA* genes encoding aerobactin synthesis and transport in hvKP virulent plasmids [27]. So that the production of aerobactin can provide iron supply for hvKP to survive.

2.2.3. Colibactin

A recent study found a virulence factor called colibactin, a small genotoxic molecule produced by hvKP [28]. Colibactin in the intestine is able to increase the inflammatory process by suppressing the activity of regulatory T lymphocyte cells, and trigger the formation of hvKP portal of entry to the central nervous system through the vascular [29]. In addition, the production of colibactin by hvKP can mediate the translocation of infection to the meninges of mice [29]. Colibactin has a very influential effect on the ability of hvKP to infect the multiorgan system, through the mechanism of inducing inflammation and colonization.

2.2.4. Plasmid pLVPK

Large virulence plasmids (pLVPK, such as pk2044 plasmid) were detected in all hvKP genomes. This Plasmid encodes aerobactin, salmochelin, and RmpA, which are found in some hvKP isolates. There was a significant decrease virulence in CC23 strains that did not have pLVPK [30]. This suggests an important role of this plasmid in *hypervirulence K. pneumoniae*. In addition, genomic comparisons revealed differences in the pathogenicity variant island (KPHP1208) specifically associated with CC23. Most CC23 isolates contain genes encoding yersiniabactin, colibactin, and microcin E492, in the pathogenicity island of KPHP1208 [31].

2.2.5. Lipopolysaccharide Antigen O and Fimbrae

Antigen O is the endotoxin found in gram negative bacteria including hvKP. antigens O in particular type O1 are thought to contribute to bacterial virulence by a mechanism of reducing macrophage activation and promoting bacteremia [32]. In addition, there are also fimbriae, especially type 3, in fimbriae type 3 is known to mediate the formation of biofilms on the abiotic surface and affect the availability of iron for metabolic processes and hvKP survival [33,34].

3. Pathophysiology and Clinical Feature

3.1. Pathophysiology

3.1.1. Portal of Entry

In early hvKP infection, direct contact route through micro-and macro-aspiration that the formation of colonization in the oropharyngeal can lead to pneumonia. In perineal colonization this occur via the ascending route and can be a urinary tract infection [35]. In some patients, cryptogenic hepatic abscesses due to hvKP associated with colon carcinoma [34]. In other studies show colibactin production by hvKP can help the translocation of infection to the meninges of mice and greatly affect the ability of hvKP translocation to the multiorgan system [36]. However, in most patients who develop hvKP infection, the initial route remains unclear.

3.1.2. Colonization

Once hvKP has successfully infected the host, the next stage is colonization. Colibactin aids the colonization process of hvKP, by the mechanism of enhancing the inflammatory process by suppressing the activity of regulatory T lymphocyte cells [36]. Microcin E492 is a bacteriocin that is active against *Enterobacteriaceae*. That activity requires the attachment of salmochelin that facilitate the uptake microcin to the target bacteria. HvKP strains produce a combination of colibactin, microcin E492, and salmochelin, which is thought to be significantly beneficial in the colonization process. Several genes have been identified using signature-tagged mutagenesis, which appear to play a role in some combination of intestinal colonization and/or invasion across the intragastric mucosal barrier in mice [36].

3.1.3. Growth and survival

hvKP strains have been shown to be more resistant to phagocytosis, neutrophil, complement mediated activity, and neutrophil extracellular traps (NETS) than *classical K. pneumoniae* strain [37]. This factor is a major impact on the survival of hvKP from eradication of the immune system. However, an important condition contributing to the hvKP phenotype is the ability to increase the amount of capsular polysaccharides. It is mediated by RmpA and/or RmpA2, which are hvKP-specific factors located in hvKP plasmids [38]. hvKP has the ability to escape from phagocytosis and neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) which are suspected of strong hypermucoviscous phenotype mediated by capsular polysaccharide regulator RmpA [21]. In studies using hvKP strains, capsular polysaccharides have been shown to protect against phagocytosis and defensin-mediated bactericidal activity, and these attenuate human defensin production in vitro [39]. Moreover, the synthesis of aerobactin molecules by iucABCD and iutA genes on hvKP virulent plasmids [27], also plays a role in improving the ability of hvKP to carry out iron acquisition to survive and increase colonization.

3.1.4. Tissue Damage

hvKP infection often leads to abscess formation. However, until now the explanation is still limited. The most probable factor is colibactin, which has been shown to be genotoxic, causing DNA damage and cell death [40]. However, there are some strains of hvKP that do not produce colibactin (for example, the non-cg23-K1 capsule type) but can also cause abscesses to form. This suggests the possibility that unknown factors may also be contributing to the occurrence of abscesses by hvKP strains. Beside that, the immune response of the host body that is not well regulated also contributes to damage to the body [29].

3.2. Signs and Symptoms

There are several clinical symptoms caused by hvKP infection in puppy as test animals, such neurological disorders, like decreased consciousness to death, swelling of the joints and even decreased body motoric, several other signs, namely septic arthritis or cellulitis [41]. There are also other symptoms in the ocular such as formation of hypopyon and blepharospasm, rise of the body temperature with the highest temperature 40°C. There are also some non-specific symptoms such as polyarthritis, pyothorax, suppurative meningitis and subdural hemorrhage [41].

Studies conducted in Taiwan found that patients who had been infected with hvKP showed several signs and symptoms such as fever, chills, abdominal pain, nausea and vomiting [42]. It was also reported that of 800 patients infected with hvKP with liver abscess one-third of patients had complications to other organs such as endophthalmitis or uveitis, empyema, meningitis, brain and epidural abscess [42, 43, 44].

Table 1 Clinical Feature differentiating *hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP) and *classical K. pneumoniae* (cKP) (38)

Nu.	Parameter	hvKP	cKP
1	Location of Infection	Commonly the community	Commonly Hospital acquired
2	Host	All ages, often healthy host	Older with some comorbid
3	Hepatic Abscess	Usually	Usually in the presence of biliary disease
4	Site of Infection	Often Multiple	Usually single
5	Infectious Syndrome	Endophthalmitis, meningitis, brain abscess, necrotizing fasciitis, splenic abscess, epidural abscess	None

Table foot note should be Font size 8, Cambria, Centre aligned, No space before paragraph

4. Conclusion

First clinical case of *hypervirulent K. pneumoniae* (hvKP) reported in Taiwan 1986 with clinical feature liver abscess with septic endophthalmitis, and some patient have extrahepatic complications such as meningitis pneumonia, prostate abscess and pyogenic ophthalmia. Another study found *K. pneumoniae* cause liver abscess have *hypermucoviscous* phenotype as the main characteristic, which is defined through the string test positive. There are several virulence factor which can support growth and survival rate of hvKP such as capsule polysaccharide, aerobactin, colibactin, plasmid pLVPK, Lipopolysaccharide Antigen O type O1 and Fimbrae type 3. The pathophysiology of hvKP still unclear but there several explanation such as hvKP strains demonstrated resistant to phagocytosis, neutrophil, complement mediated activity, and neutrophil extracellular traps (NETS) because hvKP has ability to increase the amount of capsular polysaccharides. It is mediated by RmpA and/or RmpA2 this factor major impact on the survival of hvKP. This review consequently, awareness and perspective on the characteristics and clinical feature of hvKP, are urgently required to get better understanding and providing appropriate treatment in cases of infection caused by hvKP.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of Conflict of interest

No conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Togawa A, Toh H, Onozawa K, Yoshimura M, Tokushige C, Shimono N, et al. Influence of the bacterial phenotypes on the clinical manifestations in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* bacteremia patients: A retrospective cohort study. *Journal of Infection and Chemotherapy*. 2015 Jul;21(7):531–7.
- [2] Restuccia PA, Cunha BA. *Klebsiella*. *Infect Control*. 1984 Jul;5(7):343–7.
- [3] Feldman C, Ross S, Mahomed AG, Omar J, Smith C. The aetiology of severe community-acquired pneumonia and its impact on initial, empiric, antimicrobial chemotherapy. *Respir Med*. 1995 Mar;89(3):187–92.
- [4] Liu YC. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* liver abscess associated with septic endophthalmitis. *Arch Intern Med*. 1986 Oct 1;146(10):1913–6.
- [5] Lan P, Shi Q, Zhang P, Chen Y, Yan R, Hua X, et al. Core Genome Allelic Profiles of Clinical *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Strains Using a Random Forest Algorithm Based on Multilocus Sequence Typing Scheme for Hypervirulence Analysis. *J Infect Dis*. 2020 Mar 16;221(Supplement_2):S263–71.
- [6] Lin JC, Chang FY, Fung CP, Yeh KM, Chen CT, Tsai YK, et al. Do neutrophils play a role in establishing liver abscesses and distant metastases caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae*? *PLoS One*. 2010 Nov 30;5(11):e15005.
- [7] Fang CT, Chuang YP, Shun CT, Chang SC, Wang JT. A novel virulence gene in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains causing primary liver abscess and septic metastatic complications. *J Exp Med*. 2004 Mar 1;199(5):697–705.
- [8] Zheng J xin, Lin Z wei, Sun X, Lin W hong, Chen Z, Wu Y, et al. Overexpression of OqxAB and MacAB efflux pumps contributes to eravacycline resistance and heteroresistance in clinical isolates of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Emerg Microbes Infect*. 2018 Dec 1;7(1):1–11.
- [9] Yeh KM, Kurup A, Siu LK, Koh YL, Fung CP, Lin JC, et al. Capsular Serotype K1 or K2, Rather than magA and rmpA, Is a Major Virulence Determinant for *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Liver Abscess in Singapore and Taiwan. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2007 Feb;45(2):466–71.
- [10] Lin ZW, Zheng JX, Bai B, Xu GJ, Lin FJ, Chen Z, et al. Characteristics of Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: Does Low Expression of rmpA Contribute to the Absence of Hypervirulence? *Front Microbiol*. 2020 Mar 17;11.
- [11] Russo TA, Olson R, Fang CT, Stoesser N, Miller M, MacDonald U, et al. Identification of Biomarkers for Differentiation of Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Classical *K. pneumoniae*. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2018 Sep;56(9).
- [12] Nataro JP. Pathogenesis — Thoughts from the Front Line. *Microbiol Spectr*. 2015 Jun 18;3(3).
- [13] Feldman MF, Mayer Bridwell AE, Scott NE, Vinogradov E, McKee SR, Chavez SM, et al. A promising bioconjugate vaccine against hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2019 Sep 10;116(37):18655–63.
- [14] Nassif X, Sansonetti PJ. Correlation of the virulence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* K1 and K2 with the presence of a plasmid encoding aerobactin. *Infect Immun*. 1986 Dec;54(3):603–8.
- [15] Nassif X, Fournier JM, Arondel J, Sansonetti PJ. Mucoïd phenotype of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is a plasmid-encoded virulence factor. *Infect Immun*. 1989 Feb;57(2):546–52.
- [16] Fang FC, Sandler N, Libby SJ. Liver abscess caused by magA+ *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in North America. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2005 Feb;43(2):991–2.
- [17] Lee IR, Molton JS, Wyres KL, Gorrie C, Wong J, Hoh CH, et al. Differential host susceptibility and bacterial virulence factors driving *Klebsiella* liver abscess in an ethnically diverse population. *Sci Rep*. 2016 Jul 13;6(1):29316.
- [18] Fung CP, Lin YT, Lin JC, Chen TL, Yeh KM, Chang FY, et al. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in gastrointestinal tract and pyogenic liver abscess. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2012 Aug;18(8):1322–5.
- [19] Lawlor MS, Hsu J, Rick PD, Miller VL. Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* virulence determinants using an intranasal infection model. *Mol Microbiol*. 2005 Nov;58(4):1054–73.
- [20] Paczosa MK, Meccas J. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: Going on the Offense with a Strong Defense. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews*. 2016 Sep;80(3):629–61.
- [21] Wang L, Shen D, Wu H, Ma Y. Resistance of hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* to both intracellular and extracellular killing of neutrophils. *PLoS One*. 2017 Mar 10;12(3):e0173638.
- [22] Ku YH, Chuang YC, Chen CC, Lee MF, Yang YC, Tang HJ, et al. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Isolates from Meningitis: Epidemiology, Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance. *Sci Rep*. 2017 Dec 1;7(1).
- [23] Wyres KL, Wick RR, Gorrie C, Jenney A, Follador R, Thomson NR, et al. Identification of *Klebsiella* capsule synthesis loci from whole genome data. *Microb Genom*. 2016;2(12):e000102.

- [24] Miethke M, Marahiel MA. Siderophore-Based Iron Acquisition and Pathogen Control. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews*. 2007 Sep;71(3):413–51.
- [25] Brown JS, Holden DW. Iron acquisition by Gram-positive bacterial pathogens. *Microbes Infect*. 2002 Sep;4(11):1149–56.
- [26] Russo TA, Olson R, Fang CT, Stoesser N, Miller M, MacDonald U, et al. Identification of Biomarkers for Differentiation of Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from Classical *K. pneumoniae*. *J Clin Microbiol*. 2018;56(9).
- [27] Bailey DC, Alexander E, Rice MR, Drake EJ, Mydy LS, Aldrich CC, et al. Structural and functional delineation of aerobactin biosynthesis in hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2018 May;293(20):7841–52.
- [28] Nougayrède JP, Homburg S, Taieb F, Boury M, Brzuszkiewicz E, Gottschalk G, et al. *Escherichia coli* Induces DNA Double-Strand Breaks in Eukaryotic Cells. *Science* (1979). 2006 Aug 11;313(5788):848–51.
- [29] Lu MC, Chen YT, Chiang MK, Wang YC, Hsiao PY, Huang YJ, et al. Colibactin contributes to the hypervirulence of pks+ K1 CC23 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in mouse meningitis infections. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2017 Mar 31;7(MAR).
- [30] Lin YC, Lu MC, Tang HL, Liu HC, Chen CH, Liu K Sen, et al. Assessment of hypermucoviscosity as a virulence factor for experimental *Klebsiella pneumoniae* infections: Comparative virulence analysis with hypermucoviscosity-negative strain. *BMC Microbiol*. 2011;11.
- [31] Struve C, Roe CC, Stegger M, Stahlhut SG, Hansen DS, Engelthaler DM, et al. Mapping the Evolution of Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *mBio*. 2015 Jul 21;6(4):e00630.
- [32] Lugo JZ, Price S, Miller JE, Ben-David I, Merrill VJ, Mancuso P, et al. LIPOPOLYSACCHARIDE O-ANTIGEN PROMOTES PERSISTENT MURINE BACTEREMIA. *Shock*. 2007 Feb;27(2):186–91.
- [33] Wu MF, Yang CY, Lin TL, Wang JT, Yang FL, Wu SH, et al. Humoral Immunity against Capsule Polysaccharide Protects the Host from magA + *Klebsiella pneumoniae* -Induced Lethal Disease by Evading Toll-Like Receptor 4 Signaling. *Infect Immun*. 2009 Feb;77(2):615–21.
- [34] Shon AS, Bajwa RPS, Russo TA. Hypervirulent (hypermucoviscous) *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: a new and dangerous breed. *Virulence*. 2013 Feb 15;4(2):107–18.
- [35] Qu K, Liu C, Wang ZX, Tian F, Wei JC, Tai MH, et al. Pyogenic liver abscesses associated with nonmetastatic colorectal cancers: An increasing problem in Eastern Asia. *Eastern Asia World J Gastroenterol*. 2012;18(23):2948–55.
- [36] Lu MC, Chen YT, Chiang MK, Wang YC, Hsiao PY, Huang YJ, et al. Colibactin Contributes to the Hypervirulence of pks+ K1 CC23 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in Mouse Meningitis Infections. *Front Cell Infect Microbiol*. 2017 Mar 31;7.
- [37] Pomakova DK, Hsiao CB, Beanan JM, Olson R, MacDonald U, Keynan Y, et al. Clinical and phenotypic differences between classic and hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: an emerging and under-recognized pathogenic variant. *Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis*. 2012 Jun;31(6):981–9.
- [38] Russo TA, Marr CM. Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [Internet]. 2019. Available from: <https://journals.asm.org/journal/cmr>
- [39] Cortés G, Borrell N, de Astorza B, Gómez C, Sauleda J, Albertí S. Molecular analysis of the contribution of the capsular polysaccharide and the lipopolysaccharide O side chain to the virulence of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a murine model of pneumonia. *Infect Immun*. 2002 May;70(5):2583–90.
- [40] Murakami E, Shionoya T, Komenoi S, Suzuki Y, Sakane F. Cloning and characterization of novel testis-Specific diacylglycerol kinase η splice variants 3 and 4. *PLoS One*. 2016 Sep 1;11(9).
- [41] Michael SA, Hayman DTS, Gray R, Roe WD. Clinical parameters of hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* disease and ivermectin treatment in New Zealand sea lion (*Phocarcos hookeri*) pups. *PLoS One*. 2022 Mar 3;17(3):e0264582.
- [42] Siu LK, Yeh KM, Lin JC, Fung CP, Chang FY. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* liver abscess: a new invasive syndrome. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2012 Nov;12(11):881–7.
- [43] Cheng DL, Liu YC, Yen MY, Liu CY, Wang RS. Septic metastatic lesions of pyogenic liver abscess. Their association with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* bacteremia in diabetic patients. *Arch Intern Med*. 1991 Aug;151(8):1557–9.
- [44] Patel PK, Russo TA, Karchmer AW. Hypervirulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. *Open Forum Infect Dis*. 2014 Mar;1(1):ofu028.